

ENVIRONMENTAL ADVOCACY PROGRAM FOR GRADE 11 STUDENTS OF BAUAN TECHNICAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess the environmental advocacy program for Grade 11 students of Bauan Technical High School during the school year 2018 – 2019. It also aimed to assess the level of environmental awareness of students in terms of environmental concept and issues; the environmental attitude relative to personal, school and local government responsibilities; extent of participation of the respondents and the constraints met by the teachers in the different environmental activities by the students relative to discipline, waste segregation and waste disposal. Researcher - constructed questionnaires were used to gather the information from the respondents. The researcher utilized the statistical tools such as frequency count, weighted mean, ranking and Pearson r to process the information obtained from the respondents. Pearson r was used to determine the relationship among environmental awareness, attitudes and participation of the respondents. The result of the study showed that respondent's environmental awareness of the concept and issue was moderate. Moreover, the respondents agreed on personal, school, and local government duties when it comes to environmental attitudes. In terms of environmental participation, it was revealed that there is only a moderate level of participation. The findings of the study that pertained to the relationship of environmental awareness and extent of participation was found to be significant. Furthermore, the environmental attitude was found to be significantly related to the extent of participation. Finally, an environmental advocacy program for Bauan Technical High School students was established in order to deepen and increase the student's environmental awareness. Some recommendations were given based on the findings, such as curriculum developer training, active teaching approaches, and the execution of specified activities.

Keywords: Education, Environment, Questionnaire, Philippines